

Local Government in Poland

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Poland.....	3
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Poland: An Introduction	12
2.2. <i>The Provision of Local Public Transport</i>	15
2.3. <i>Provision of Internet Infrastructure by Local Government: A Step Towards Smart Villages</i>	18
2.4. <i>Lack of Effective Housing Management in Communes and Attempts to Recover from the Crisis</i> ...	25
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Poland: An Introduction	32
3.2. <i>Investment Expenditure of Local Governments: The Role of European Funds in the Financial Strategies of Rural gminas</i>	42
3.3. <i>Integrated Territorial Investment (ITI)</i>	46
3.4. <i>The Importance of the ‘Village Fund’ for the Mobilization of Rural Residents to Civic Participation</i>	50
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Poland: An Introduction	56
4.2. <i>What does Metropolitan Cooperation in the Functional Area of the Capital Warsaw Involve?</i>	62
4.3. <i>First Territorial Unit of Metropolitan Nature in Poland: The Metropolitan Union ‘Upper Silesian-Zagłębie Metropolis’</i>	67
4.4. <i>The Association ‘Gdansk-Gdynia-Sopot Metropolitan Area’ as an Example of Urban–Rural Cooperation</i>	75
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Poland: An Introduction.....	83
5.2. <i>Institutionalizing Intergovernmental Relations in Poland: The Joint Commission of the Government and Territorial Self-Government</i>	85
5.3. <i>County-Commune Unions as a New Form of Intergovernmental Relations in Poland: The Beskidian County and Commune Union</i>	88
5.4. <i>The Interface between Subnational and National Levels of Government: The Role of National Local Self-government Organizations</i>	94
6.1. People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making in Poland: An Introduction	102
6.2. <i>Decisions on Expanding the City Territory at the Expense of the Rural Area: Consultations with Residents or a Local Referendum?</i>	106
6.3. <i>Youth Commune Council in Poland</i>	115
6.4. <i>Participatory Fund in Cities</i>	120

1. The System of Local Government in Poland

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Types of Local Governments

Poland is a unitary state without any autonomous entities. As a consequence, a uniform system of territorial self-government exists throughout Poland. The traditions of territorial self-government date back to 1918 when, after 123 years of political oblivion, the Polish state was established. After World War II, Poland was an undemocratic and centralized state which led to, among other things, the liquidation of territorial self-government. The reconstruction of territorial self-government began in Poland with the political transformation after 1989. The first stage was the restoration of territorial self-government in communes (*gmina*) in 1990, then in 1999 the self-government in counties (*powiat*) and in voivodeships (*województwo*) was introduced.

The current Constitution of the Republic of Poland of 1997 introduces two types of territorial self-government, namely *local* self-government and *regional* self-government (Article 164). Currently in Poland (since 1999), territorial self-government is three-tier and it is structured as follows:

- self-government in communes as the basic level of local self-government;
- self-government in counties the second level of local self-government;
- self-government in voivodeships as regional self-government.

In addition, large municipalities (over 100,000 residents) may be granted the status and tasks of a counties (city with *powiat* rights/cities with *powiat* status).

Therefore, there are four levels of political representation in Poland: the state and three levels of territorial self-government.

At present (2020), there are 2,477 communes (*gmina*), including 1,555 rural *gminas*, 621 urban-rural *gminas* and 302 urban *gminas*. The population of *gminas* ranges from 1.7 million (the Capital City of Warsaw) to 1,300, and the average population of a Polish *gmina* amounts to 15,000. It means that in the comparison to other European countries, Poland's *gminas* are relatively large. If we take into account only urban *gminas*, the average population is 61,000, whereas in rural *gminas* the average population amounts to approximately 7,000. At the beginning of the political transformation in Poland in 1990, there were 2,383 *gminas*. It means that modifications introduced in the division into *gminas* have been rather minor.

Figure 1: Spatial delimitation of *gminas* in Poland¹

The second tier of the local government, i.e. the level of counties (*powiat*), was established in Poland in 1999. At present, there are 314 *powiats* and 66 cities with *powiat* status. The population of *powiats* range from 21,500 to 373,500. The average population of a Polish *powiat* amounts to 82,000, whereas cities with *powiat* status have on average 191,000 inhabitants. When the territorial reform was being prepared in 1999, it was the establishment of *powiats* (as intermediate units between *gmina* and voivodeship) which gave rise to the greatest controversies. Dissenting voices against the introduction of an additional level of territorial structure (and, in consequence, a local government unit) were not rare. Even now the issue of *powiats* is under public debate, mainly due to the problem of the financing of *powiat* local government as well as functional weakness of smaller *powiats* (Polish *powiats* are small units in comparison to their counterparts in other European countries). The formation of seven new *powiats* in 2002 was the last major modification in the map of *powiats*.

¹ 'Types of *gminas* and urban and rural areas' (*Statistics Poland*, 2020) <<https://stat.gov.pl/en/regional-statistics/classification-of-territorial-units/administrative-division-of-poland/types-of-gminas-and-urban-and-rural-areas/>> accessed 2 November 2019.

The third level of territorial structure applies to voivodeships (*województwo*). The voivodeships correspond to the NUTS-2 regions (according to the European Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics),² which are the basis for regional operational programs co-financed by the European Union. The year 1999 marked a crucial point in shaping the territory and political system of voivodeships. After lengthy preparations accompanied by political disputes, it was decided to form 16 voivodeships. It meant a departure from territorial fragmentation on a regional level (in the years 1975-1999 there were as many as 49 voivodeships in Poland). As a result of an enlarged territory, voivodeships as regions gained the right to self-government—thus, another stage of decentralization of Poland was reached. So far, the number of voivodeships has not been changed.³

Legal Status of Local Governments

The inclusion of the principle of subsidiarity⁴ in the preamble to the Constitution of the Republic of Poland of 1997 and the principle of decentralization⁵ in the first chapter of the Constitution is of key importance for the legal status of self-government in Poland. Article 16 provides legal guarantees for local authorities: '(i) The inhabitants of the units of basic territorial division shall form a self-governing community in accordance with law. (ii) Local government shall participate in the exercise of public power. The substantial part of public duties which local government is empowered to discharge by statute shall be done in its own name and under its own responsibility.'

A comprehensive regulation concerning territorial self-government is contained in Chapter VII ('Local government') of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland of 1997.

Territorial self-government is based on democratic legitimacy. At each level, residents elect a representative body (the number of councilors currently ranges from 15 to 51, with the exception of Warsaw with 60 councilors). In addition, the head of the executive body (mayor) has been elected directly by the residents at the *gmina* level since 2002. Moreover, the Constitution of Poland guarantees residents of *gminas*, *powiats* and voivodeships the right to directly settle matters through the institution of a local referendum. A referendum on self-taxation of residents for public purposes is a special type of the local referendum. However, such a referendum can only be held at the *gmina* level.

² Eurostat, 'Background' <<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/background>> accessed 2 November 2019.

³ Mirska Andželika, 'State policy on the formation and modernisation of Polish territorial structure' in Europäisches Zentrum für Föderalismus-Forschung Tübingen EZFF (ed), *Jahrbuch des Föderalismus 2018: Föderalismus, Subsidiarität und Regionen in Europa* (Nomos 2018).

⁴ 'Hereby establish this Constitution of the Republic of Poland as the basic law for the State, based on respect for freedom and justice, cooperation between the public powers, social dialogue as well as on the principle of subsidiarity in the strengthening the powers of citizens and their communities'.

⁵ Article 15: 'The territorial system of the Republic of Poland shall ensure the decentralization of public power'.

Local government shall perform public tasks not reserved by the Constitution or statutes to the organs of other public authorities (Article 163 of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland of 1997). *Gmina* self-government, which has been granted the presumption of competence in matters of territorial self-government, is of fundamental importance. Article 164 establishes the following: '(i) The commune (*gmina*) shall be the basic unit of local government. (ii) Other units of regional and/or local government shall be specified by statute. (iii) The commune shall perform all tasks of local government not reserved to other units of local government.'

Territorial self-government units are subject to the Constitution of the Republic of Poland and the Acts of the Polish State. Three system acts are of fundamental importance:

- the Act of 8 March 1990 on *Gmina* Self-Government,
- the Act of 5 June 1998 on *Powiat* Self-Government,
- the Act of 5 June 1998 on Voivodeship Self-Government.

The only criterion of supervision over the activity of self-government is the criterion of legality, supervision is exercised by government administration authorities (the Prime Minister, voivodes⁶ and regarding financial matters - regional audit chambers). However, any disputes between the government administration and territorial self-government shall be settled by an administrative court. There are no authoritative interrelations between the tiers of territorial self-government – only voluntary cooperation is possible.

The Constitution divides public tasks performed by self-government into own tasks (financed from the budget of a self-government unit) and commissioned tasks (financed from the state budget).

Gmina self-government performs a wide range of public tasks which include, among others, issues related to local technical infrastructure, social infrastructure, education, health and order protection and safety. In accordance with the principle of subsidiarity, the *powiat* self-government 'assists' *gmina* in performing local tasks that exceed the capacity of a *gmina* ('supra-communal' local tasks). While the self-government of *gmina* and *powiat* implements a number of public services for local communities on an ongoing basis, the main role of voivodeship self-government is to facilitate economic development of regions. Among other things, the task of the voivodeship self-government is to manage EU structural funds.

⁶ The voivodes (16) shall be the representative of the Council of Ministers in voivodeships. They are appointed by the Prime Minister. *Voivodeships* are the highest-level administrative subdivision of Poland.

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

There are three types of *gminas*:

- urban *gminas* (their boundaries correspond with the boundaries of the city forming the municipality);
- urban-rural *gminas*, which include both cities within administrative boundaries and areas outside city boundaries;
- rural *gminas* without cities within their territory.

Cities in Poland are towns and cities with city rights (granted by the central government). However, it is a formal classification based solely on an administrative criterion. The Act on *Gmina* Self-Government does not differentiate the tasks of according to this classification – all *gminas* have the same scope of activity. The exceptions are large urban *gminas* which also have the status of *powiat* (city with *powiat* rights). They carry out the tasks of both *gmina* and *powiat*. Currently, there are 66 of them and the general criterion for their establishment is a population over 100,000. However, some local government politicians claim that this threshold should be reduced to 50,000⁷.

On the other hand, the need is recognized to merge the cities with the *powiat* rights and *powiats* whose authorities are seated in the said cities due to significant disproportions in the institutional potential of *powiats*. Government analyses indicated a significantly higher potential of cities with *powiat* rights and a particularly low potential of *powiats* without large urban centers. The data show that *powiats* without large cities have significantly scarcer resources allocated to the fulfilment of public tasks of *powiats*⁸.

Public tasks may be performed by individual self-government units independently or by way of cooperation with other self-government units (inter-municipal cooperatives). Self-governments of a given level may cooperate with each other (cooperation between *gminas*, between *powiats*, between voivodeships). Moreover, cooperation between the levels is also possible: since 2016, unions of *powiats* and *gminas* may be established. The form of the *powiat-gmina* union is intended for the implementation of tasks that exceed the competence of one tier of self-government. The aim was to enhance the independence and operational flexibility of territorial self-government units. It can also be interpreted as an attempt to address the problems occurring mainly in metropolitan areas.

The legal form of the union of *gminas* (union of *powiats*, union of *gmina* and *powiat*) requires the establishment of a new legal person to perform part of the tasks of the self-government. Unions of *gminas* are a very popular form of performing self-government tasks (currently there

⁷ 'Interpelacja nr 5867 do Ministra Spraw Wewnętrznych i Administracji' (*Sejm Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej*) <<http://orka2.sejm.gov.pl/IZ5.nsf/main/2AE373E5>> accessed 1 July 2019.

⁸ 'Zasadniczy, trójstopniowy podział terytorialny państwa' (*Ministerstwo Spraw Wewnętrznych i Administracji*, 31 May 2001) <<https://archiwum.mswia.gov.pl/pl/aktualnosci/1644,dok.html>> accessed 1 July 2019.

are 313 of them in Poland and they include from 2 to 49 *gminas*). There are 7 *powiat* unions and 8 *powiat-gmina* unions. Their tasks involve mainly the organization of common local public transport. The same applies to education as only a uniform system of education from primary schools (which is the responsibility of *gminas*) to secondary schools (which are subject to *powiats*) can resolve demographic problems or fulfil the expectations of the local labor market.

The performed public tasks may also be modified through ‘delegating’ public tasks by a territorial self-government unit to another territorial self-government unit. This is done by way of a voluntary agreement.

‘Commissioning’ tasks to the self-government by the government administration is a different matter – if they are commissioned by virtue of the law, they are imposed on the self-government ‘from the top’ (together, of course, with financial resources from the Polish state budget). Polish self-governments indicate that those funds are often insufficient.

Political and Social Context in Poland

Compared to other countries, the national political parties are in Poland not very strongly represented at the local government level.⁹ To gain a stronger voice, self-governments attempted to create a nationwide political movement of mayors of large cities. For example, in 2011 Union of Mayors – Citizens to the Senate¹⁰ (*Unia Prezydentów – Obywatele do Senatu*) was established and it put forward its candidates in the elections to the upper house of the Polish Parliament – Senate (majority voting system applies). The Local Government Movement ‘Non-Partisans’ (*Ruch Samorządowy ‘Bezpartyjni’*) was also established, consisting of mayors and councilors. The purpose of the movement is to be an alternative to political parties in local government elections (primarily at the level of the voivodeship self-government).

However, if we analyze the results of local government elections, the influence of national political parties clearly diminishes, the lower the level of government. Starting from the highest level, i.e. the 16 voivodeship self-governments, it is basically political parties that dominate the elections to the voivodeship assemblies. In the local government elections of 2018, candidates of national parties received a total of 89.4 per cent of votes. The Local Government Movement ‘Non-Partisans’ gained 5.28 per cent of the country's vote. Regional groupings received marginal support, except for three voivodeships. In the Opolskie Voivodeship, ‘The German Minority Electoral Committee’ traditionally receives strong support (in 2018 – 14.64 per cent). In two other voivodships, regional movements concentrated around local politicians obtained:

⁹ Bukowski Michał, Jarosław Flis, Agnieszka Hess and Agnieszka Szymańska, *Rządzący i opozycja, partie sejmowe i lokalne w małopolskich wyborach samorządowych 2014* (Attyka 2016) 24.

¹⁰ The Senate is the upper house of the Polish Parliament, the lower house is the Sejm. The Senate and the Sejm exercises legislative power in Poland. The Members of both houses are elected by direct election. The Senate consists of 100 senators, the Senate - 460 deputies.

8.29 per cent of votes (the Lower Silesian Voivodeship: Electoral Committee of Voters ‘With Dutkiewicz for Lower Silesia’¹¹) and 5.26 per cent of votes (the Świętokrzyskie Voivodeship: Electoral Committee of Voters ‘Wenta¹²’s Świętokrzyskie Project’.

At the *powiat* level, the presence of parties in the elections is weaker, in the 2018 elections the national parties won about 62 per cent of votes. At the level of *gminas*, the parties have obviously the smallest influence – local election initiatives prevail. In *gminas* with up to 20,000 inhabitants (single-mandate constituencies) national parties won about 27 per cent of votes. In *gminas* with over 20 000 inhabitants the figure was approx. 50 per cent.¹³ In rural *gminas*, traditionally, the peasants’ party – the Polish People’s Party (*Polskie Stronnictwo Ludowe*) – has played an important role. In the last elections, the importance of the Law and Justice Party (*Prawo i Sprawiedliwość*) has increased, reflecting the situation at the national government level.

The number and share of rural population in the total population of the country is declining. At the end of 2017, the rural population accounted for 39.9 per cent (in 1950 over 63 per cent)¹⁴. The *gminas*’ population forecasts of the Polish Central Statistical Office (GUS) for 2017-2030 indicate, above all, a strong development of major urban agglomerations with adjacent areas. They will continue to attract people from more peripheral areas. At the same time, a continuation of the suburbanization process should be expected, which will lead to a significant increase in population in the *gminas* adjacent to big cities.¹⁵ These changes are caused by lower prices of flats or house building costs and reflect the growing economic status which enables inhabitants to move to an area more beneficial in terms of being a ‘greener environment’.¹⁶ In 2018, 55 cities with *powiat* rights (there are 66 cities of this type in total) recorded a decrease in population compared to the previous year. These included cities that aspire to play the role of a metropolis (Poznań, Łódź, Bydgoszcz). Warsaw, the capital city of Poland recorded an

¹¹ Rafał Dudkiewicz was from 2002 to 2018 the Mayor of Wrocław, the capital city of the Lower Silesian Voivodeship.

¹² Bogdan Wenta having run from his own committee and was *elected* as Mayor of Kielce, the capital of the Świętokrzyskie Voivodeship. For years related with handball, first as a player of the Polish national team and Germany. 2004 - 2012 was the coach of the Polish national handball team. One of the best handball player in history of Polish handball.

¹³ National Electoral Commission, ‘The Results of Local Elections 2018’ (*Local Government Elections 2018*, 30 June 2018) <<https://wybory2018.pkw.gov.pl/pl/dane-w-arkuszach>> accessed 14 December 2019.

¹⁴ Stańczak Joanna and Znajewska Agnieszka, ‘Population in Poland: Size and Structure by Territorial Division as of June 30, 2017’ (Central Statistical Office, 2017) <https://stat.gov.pl/files/gfx/portalinformacyjny/pl/defaultaktualnosci/5468/6/22/1/ludnosc._stan_i_struktura_w_przekroju_terytoryalnym._stan_w_dniu_30.06.2017.pdf> accessed 1 December 2019.

¹⁵ ‘Prognoza ludności gmin na lata 2017-2030’ (*Statistics Poland*, 31 August 2017) <<https://stat.gov.pl/obszary-tematyczne/ludnosc/prognoza-ludnosci/prognoza-ludnosci-gmin-na-lata-2017-2030-opracowanie-eksperymentalne,10,1.html>> accessed 1 December 2019.

¹⁶ Małgorzata Waligórska, Zofia Kostrzewa, Maciej Potyra and Longina Rutkowska, ‘Population Projection 2014-2050’ (Central Statistical Office 2014) <<https://stat.gov.pl/obszary-tematyczne/ludnosc/prognoza-ludnosci/prognoza-ludnosci-na-lata-2014-2050-opracowana-2014-r-,1,5.html>> accessed 1 December 2019.

increase. The number of *gminas* with less than 5,000 inhabitants is steadily growing. There are already approx. 800 of them.

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